

On the Upper Bound for the Neighbourhood Version of the Second Zagreb Index of a Graph

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Abstract

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. For each vertex u in G , $N(u)$ is defined as $\{v : v \in V, uv \in E\}$. We use $\gamma(u)$ to denote $\sum_{v \in N(u)} d(v)$. Mondal, De, and Pal (S. Mondal, N. De, and A. Pal, On some new neighbourhood degree based indices, Acta Chemica IASI 27(2019) 31-46) introduced the neighbourhood version of the second Zagreb index which is defined as $\sum_{uv \in E} \gamma(u)\gamma(v)$. In this short note, we present upper bounds for the neighbourhood version of the second Zagreb index of a graph.

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1 Introduction

We consider only finite undirected graphs without loops or multiple edges. Notation and terminology not defined here follow those in [1]. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph with n vertices and e edges. For each vertex u in G , $N(u)$ is defined as $\{v : v \in V, uv \in E\}$. We use $\gamma(u)$ to denote $\sum_{v \in N(u)} d(v)$. The clique number and chromatic number of a graph G are denoted respectively by $\omega(G)$ and $\chi(G)$.

The first and second Zagreb indices were introduced by Gutman and Trinajstić in [6] (also see [7]). For a graph G , its first Zagreb index, denoted $M_1(G)$, and second Zagreb index, denoted $M_2(G)$, are defined respectively as $\sum_{u \in V} d^2(u)$ and $\sum_{uv \in E} d(u)d(v)$. Motivated by the definitions of $M_1(G)$ and $M_2(G)$, Mondal, De, and Pal in [8] introduced several neighbourhood degree based indices for a graph G and obtained some results on the indices in the same paper. One of those indices is the neighbourhood version of the second Zagreb index $M_2^*(G)$ which is defined as $\sum_{uv \in E} \gamma(u)\gamma(v)$. In this short note, we present upper bounds for the neighborhood version of the second Zagreb index of a graph. The main result of this note is as follows.

Theorem 1 Let G be a graph with n vertices and e edges. If U is any upper bound for $M_1(G)$. Then

$$M_2^* \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\omega}\right) M_1^2 \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\omega}\right) U^2.$$

2 Proofs

Proof of Theorem 1. In order to prove Theorem 1, we need the following result in [9].

Suppose $G = (V, E)$ is a graph of order n such that $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$. Let $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ be any n -vector with $x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n = 1$ and $x_i \geq 0$ for each i , $1 \leq i \leq n$. Then

$$\sum_{v_i v_j \in E} x_i x_j \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\omega}\right).$$

If $e = 0$, then $\omega = 1$. Thus the inequalities in Theorem 1 are true. Now we consider the case of $e > 0$. For each vertex u in G , we define $x_u = \frac{\gamma(u)}{\sum_{u \in V} \gamma(u)}$. Then $x_u \geq 0$ and $\sum_{u \in V} x_u = 1$. Notice that $\sum_{u \in V} \gamma(u) = M_1$. Applying Lemma 1, we have

$$\sum_{uv \in E} \frac{\gamma(u)}{M_1} \frac{\gamma(v)}{M_1} = \sum_{uv \in E} x_u x_v \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\omega}\right).$$

Thus

$$M_2^* = \sum_{uv \in E} \gamma(u)\gamma(v) \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\omega}\right) M_1^2 \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\omega}\right) U^2.$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 1.

3 Applications of Theorem 1

Notice that the following result follows from the combination of results obtained by de Caen in [5] and Das in [4].

Theorem 2 Let G be a graph with n vertices and $e > 0$ edges. Then

$$M_1 \leq e \left(\frac{2e}{n-1} + n - 2 \right)$$

with equality if and only if G is a complete graph K_n , a star $K_{1,n-1}$, or a complete graph with one isolated vertex $K_{n-1} \cup K_1$.

From Theorem 1 and Theorem 2, we have the following result.

Theorem 3 Let G be a graph with n vertices and $e > 0$ edges. Then

$$M_2^* \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\omega}\right) \left(e \left(\frac{2e}{n-1} + n - 2 \right) \right)^2$$

with equality if and only if G is a complete graph K_n or a complete graph with one isolated vertex $K_{n-1} \cup K_1$.

Recall the following result which was obtained by Zhou in [10].

Theorem 4 Let G be a graph with n vertices, e edges, and without isolated vertices. Then

$$M_1 \leq n(2e - n + 1)$$

with equality if and only if G is a complete graph K_n , a star $K_{1,n-1}$, or a graph eK_2 consists of e independent edges.

From Theorem 1 and Theorem 4, we have the following result.

Theorem 5 Let G be a graph with n vertices, e edges, and without isolated vertices. Then

$$M_2^* \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\omega}\right) \left(n(2e - n + 1) \right)^2$$

with equality if and only if G is a complete graph K_n .

A variety of upper bounds for M_1 can be found in [2]. We can use those upper bounds to obtain upper bounds for M_2^* .

Notice that we can obtain the lower bounds for ω by solving the inequalities in Theorem 1. Those lower bounds are also the lower bounds for χ since $\omega \leq \chi$. In particular, if G is a k -regular graph with order n and e edges, then we have that $e = \frac{nk}{2}$, $M_1 = nk^2$, and $\gamma(u) = k^2$ for each vertex u in G . We, from Theorem 1, have that $\chi \geq \omega \geq \frac{n}{n-k}$. This lower bound for ω can be derived from the results in [3] or [5].

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